

STUDY PLOT			
1.- PLOT IDENTIFIER			
2.- ESTIMATED AGE OF THE OLIVE GROVE	Very young olive grove (0-10 years)		
	Young olive grove (10-20 years)		
	Mature olive grove (20-50 years)		
	Old olive grove (50-100 years)		
	Very old olive grove (more than 100 years)		
3.- PLANTATION FRAMEWORK	In hedge:	Row width: (a)	
		Distance between trunks (b)	
	Rectangle frame	Distance between two trees	
	Irregular planting		
4.- VARIETY OF THE OLIVE TREE			
5.- NUMBER OF TRUNKS WITHIN THE OLIVE TREE (check all that apply)	One trunk	Two trunks	Three trunks
6.- AVERAGE PRODUCTION DATA			
7.- IRRIGATION:	Yes	No	
8.- OBSERVATIONS			

PHOTOGRAPHS OF THE PLOT

SAMPLING POINTS			
1.-WP Code:			
2.-Date			
3.-Time			
4.-GPS coordinates	Latitude	Longitude	
5.-Vegetal cover	Yes	No	
6.-Phenological state of the olive grove (1 to 9)			
7.-Climatic data	Temperature	Precipitation	Wind
8.- Sampling type			
9.-Distance to the tree from the sample point (cm)			
10.- Sample depth			
11.- Person who takes data in the field	Name:		
	Surname:		
	Phone:		
	Email:		
12.-Observations			